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Annang Indigenous Apprenticeship Education: An Alternative to Western Education for the Development of Annangland

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Abstract

This study reviewed the impact of western education on the development of Annang land, in particular, and Nigeria and Africa, in general. It was discovered that western education has a dysfunctional effect on the development of the Africa because it is not tied to the pattern of work in the continent. The exotic origin and white collar orientation of western education alienates those who acquire it from agriculture which is the major occupation in Africa till today. It is also the findings of this study that there are people who are regarded as dunces in schools offering western education but are gifted in the crafts and blue collar jobs and would excel if given vocational training. The study therefore recommended that Annang land should collaborate with the relevant government agencies to focus on the indigenous apprenticeship education to encourage this category of people and foster the development of Annang land.

1. Introduction

Education is very important for the development of any society. Every society has their form of education that helps in the development of such society. Before the coming of the Europeans, Africa had its own form of education. Africa's indigenous education was directly tied to the pattern of work in the continent – agriculture, craftsmanship, etc. Unfortunately, at the advent of the Europeans, this indigenous education was replaced by Western education when Africa was moved to a state of open and undisguised political and cultural subordination.

Political sovereignty was lost and all lines of indigenous education and political organizations and consolidation were all forcefully suspended by the European invasion. New patterns of political unification were thereafter imposed from outside the continent, in utter disregard for old patterns and their unities. New developments and educational curriculum were henceforth dictated by the Europeans and were guided by non-African specifications.

Into the agrarian, pre-industrial economy of the continent, a nucleus of the industrial capitalist economy of Europe was implanted. Through a determined push, by political Acts and economic incentives from the colonial government, coupled with its industrial character, this newly implanted sector got an advantage over the pre-industrial agrarian economy. The result was that while the European industrial implantation was growing larger, stronger and dominant, the Afro-agrarian economy was diminishing and weakening, becoming more and more subordinate to the former.

Politically, the institutions and philosophies of Africa were uprooted and replaced by foreign ones. For example, African communal democracies were replaced by European pro-consular regimes and authoritarian bureaucracies. In economic terms, loss of sovereignty meant that Africans lost all control over the quantity, quality, speed and direction of their economies.

2. Methodology:

This study adopted the historical/descriptive method and uses qualitative approach to analyze the negative impact of western education on the development of Annang land, in particular, and Nigeria and Africa, in general. Textual tools were used to test the data generated through secondary sources.

3. The Negative Influence of Western Education:

Many factors contribute to the alienation of Africans from their cultural heritage. Of these factors, Western education is the most pronounced. In colonizing Africa, Britain, and indeed all colonial powers, had other aims apart from securing economic advantages for themselves. They also aimed at integrating Africa into the Western capitalist system through a continual attachment and subordination of Africans to the West. Hence all their policies were tailored to prevent Africa from freely developing its own ideas and institutions.

After gaining a foothold in the continent, the imperialists began a process of transforming Africans intellectually and morally. The principal instrument used to accomplish this goal was education. Formal education is a part and parcel of European culture. With it, the colonialists easily disseminated to Africans “the scientific principles of the material world which they discovered, as well as a body of varied philosophical reflections on man and society” (Rodney, 1973:219).

It is a truism that the full benefits of education can only be realized where the learning process is directly related to the pattern of work in the society concerned. Western education did not meet this requirement since it was imposed on the continent from outside.

Apart from this exotic origin, it has a certain cultural bias which exerts a subtle pressure on the mind of Africans and causes them to hate their nativity. The fact that they were born Africans become a sort of nightmare. The result is that they unconsciously seek to change their identity. For this purpose, the educational system provides a unique opportunity. African undergraduates enter universities as natural Africans with African hairdo, dressing and beliefs. But as raw materials fed into the production line in a factory, they come out at graduation as finished products; fully Europeanized Africans. Their hairstyle changes, their dressing also changes and their intonations are transformed in total imitation of British or American accent.

The benefit of Western education is greatly curtailed in Africa by the fact that the educational system was not designed to promote agriculture which was and still is the bedrock of the continent's economy. The education given to Africans was to enable them to read and write in order to make the exploitative relations easier for the Europeans. The curriculum was applied without regard to the African condition. This was a deliberate attempt to confuse and mystify the people. Ogunlade (1974) quoting Ashby (1964) showed that "there was a deliberate attempt to produce a type of student who is Western in his intellectual attitude towards life ... but who remains African in sympathy and desiring of respect in tribal life, custom, rule and law." The result, if we use the words of Governor Cameron of Tanganyika, would be that "the African would cease to think as an African and instead become a fair-minded Englishman" (Rodney, 1973:392).

The history that was taught in the colonial schools was about the British, French or Portuguese Empires. Whatever was discussed about African past related to European slave trade. Therefore, the educational system, according to Rodney (1973:380) was not such that was "designed to give young Africans confidence and pride as members of African societies, but one which sought to instill a sense of deference towards all that was European and capitalist."

The principal objective of the colonial education was the dissemination of European knowledge by teaching the arts, science, philosophy and literature of Europe, and the intention was to create a class of people that were native in blood and colour, but English in tastes, in opinions, in morals and intellect (Rodney, 1973).

Through this subtle way, Britain succeeded in making the educated Africans to prefer English language to their native tongue; English writers and their books appealed more to Africans than African writers and their books; European food also became more superior

to these educated Africans than African food, and European mode of life was desired in place of the indigenous culture.

In the same way, they preferred a wholesale replication of British University to Africa even though the curriculum of such University was not suitable to the African milieu. The African intellectual, educated in London or Cambridge or Manchester, would have been indignant at any softening of standards, any substitution of easier options, any cheapened version of higher education (Rodney, 1973).

Although the colonialists had the foresight and intention to adapt the curriculum of Western education to suit agriculture, some of the educated Africans were vehemently opposed to this. One Guinean is quoted by Rodney (1973:427) as reacting to France's recommendation to adapt education to suit agriculture, which is the major occupation of Guinea, with these words; "we want a metropolitan curriculum and the same diploma as in France for we are as French as the French of the metropolises"

In their eagerness to acquire the original form of Western education, Africans have also adopted the class bias, the racism, cultural boastfulness and the materialism inherent in Western education. This has made western educated Africans to see agriculture as an anathema. According to Otonti (1964:170),

It was neither the science, philosophy, nor even the religion of the West which most impressed the natives; it was the material wealth together with the power which was associated with it, which caught their imaginations. The 'palaces' in which Europeans live together with all the material comfort which surrounded them impressed the natives more strongly than anything else.

This, according to him, has led to the culture of 'greed, avarice, ruthlessness, sharp practices, and even dishonesty and corruption' in African politics today. He wrote; "almost every means, it seems justifies the supreme end, the attainment of material riches. Those who are fortunate enough to have some wealth, want more, and are anxious to corner all the available wealth for themselves and their families."

The decision of the colonial government to establish universities in the continent was to help Africans think European and act European. Even though the establishment of the university was in response to the demand of the National Council of British West Africa (N.C.B.W.A.), the university established was not suitable to the stage of development of the continent. The education given to Africans was totally divorced from the productive

activity, and there was a division between manual and intellectual education. The educational system was totally detached from the nature and experience of Africans and instead, had a bookish base and a white-collar orientation. Most of the first group of Africans that had the ‘privilege’ of western education specialized in Classics. They were encouraged to take on English as a major so that at graduation they could be useful to the colonial government as interpreters and administrators.

Colonial education also introduced the capitalist principle of individualism and personal achievement into the African society. And this has undermined the family ties which were a source of cohesion in the continent. Skinner (1980:15) quoted a circular letter written in 1877 by Colonel Trinitarian, the Governor of French Sudan to his subordinates. The circular reads;

In the Sudan we are in contact with a population which has been defeated militarily, but which now must be conquered intellectually and morally. We must therefore attract these people to us, interact regularly with them so that we can take away their spirit, impose our ideas upon them and brand them with our particular stamp.

This was the crux of the French policy of assimilation which was to be effected through education. In the first lesson of the text used by African pupils in French schools, the youngsters learned, “my new country from today is France. I am French. And when I grow up, every Sunday, I shall place the Tricolour on the top of my house and shall say to my subjects, ‘there is a beautiful flag’.”

On their part, the British, though not as assiduous as the French, succeeded in convincing the Africans that their lot lay with the British Empire. This policy was perfected by integrating all Anglo-African countries into the British Commonwealth after independence. The result is the appearance of a group of Africans who have acquired the cultures of the colonizers and considered themselves to be British, French or Portuguese. They have learned to consider Europe as their home and have adopted European clothing, speech and mannerisms. In the words of Frantz Fanon, the Africans having “judged, condemned, abandoned his cultural forms, his language, his food habits, his sexual behaviour, his ways of settling down, of resting, of laughing, of enjoying himself, the oppressed flings himself upon the imposed culture with the desperation of a drowning man” (Zahar, 1974:42).

This was the result of the racial stereotype designed by the colonialists to make their subjects hate themselves for being who they were. They did this through institutional and

personal discrimination perfected with administrative measures and sanctions. At school, children were taught the logical connotations of the various words, in particular, the value judgments attached to the antonyms “black” and “white.” The children were taught that anything black is evil and anything white is good. Today, Africans have come to accept the European representation of Satan as a black creature with horns and a pitch folk while, in reality, the Bible depicts him as white, just as other angels. The increasing use of expressions, proverbs and parables which were disparaging to the black origin coupled with the language of the colonizer with which these things were taught led the children to identify with what they learned, and apply the racial stereotype, first, to other blacks, and ultimately to themselves.

On the administrative sphere, the British policy of Indirect Rule created a clear-cut division from the onset and institutionalized the social distance and the purported differences existing between the colonial overlords, and the colonized. Ohonbamu (1969) wrote that during the period of our colonial tutelage, we were consciously tutored to believe in and accept our inherent inferiority. We were only natives, immature, backward, ignorant and primitive Africans incapable of governing ourselves. We were told that we could never catch up with the white and civilized Western world. Our dark skin is the embodiment of backwardness and the outward sign of inferiority. This situation compelled Africans in seeking a chance for self-assertion and advancement in the colonial hierarchy to simply imitate the English way of life and freely adopt imported elements of British culture and civilization.

The impression has become permanent on the mind of the average African that the whites are superior; that our best can only be equivalent to the worse of the white man, and that we can never be as good as they except we copy them. That is why many Africans still think and believe that everything coming from West is the best. They inherently look to the West for everything. Thus, for more fifty years after independence, African countries are still experimenting with exotic forms of government. If a system is not borrowed from Britain or the United States of America, Africans believe it cannot work.

Balandier (1966:70), writing about his observation among the educated class in Lagos in the early sixties, said:

Some of its members have lost interest in that Africa devoid of material goods and cultural riches ... They have acquired a taste of the English way of life ... They have become refined in imitation of their educators ... Their

political ambitions stop at a democracy which would have the innocuousness of their plush interiors.

Balandier sadly observed that it is these same people that formed the leadership of the nationalist movements, and they saw “freedom” from a perspective different from that of the masses which they controlled. All these can be traced to the education they received.

This point was not lost to Skinner (1980:44). To him, “one reason that Africa is still not psycho-culturally free from outside influence is that by and large its educational systems are patterned on those of the former colonial powers.” Ashby (1964) and Arnold (1977) agree completely that African education is still largely an importation of the British model. According to Ashby (1964:47), the universities pattern the civic universities of England. And “like these universities, therefore, they are constitutionally autonomous and detached from the state. In standards and curriculum, they emphasized the thin stream of academic excellence and the narrow specialism. In social function they regarded themselves as restricted to an elite.”

Thus, the first two universities established in West Africa, the University College, Ibadan and the University College, Ghana, bore the unmistakable image of their British origin, exhibiting the superficial and fripperies of British academic life signified by gowns, high tables, convocations, etc. The University College, Ibadan did not only follow strictly, the traditions of British universities, but there was also the desire to emulate even the fashions of British academic life. This is the origin of the adoption of the outward trappings of the English gentlemen by African undergraduates.

This has become pervasive, nay, epidemic. In the words of Agbese, “We are fenced in by foreigners, foreign names, foreign food and foreign things”. Thus, through Western education, pride, selfishness and nepotism have been entrenched in African politics leading to the problem of “sit-tight” politicians who want to rule for 2nd, 3rd, 4th and even 5th terms to the exclusion of others. This has hindered smooth succession in African politics.

Year after year, the educational system churns out graduates that roam the street with degrees in search for jobs. This is different from what is practiced elsewhere. In China, the education given to the citizenry is directly tied to the productive activity – manufacturing. Engineering students in China are given practical assignments that enable them to manufacture from simple appliances like phones to more sophisticated machines as they progress in their academic careers. At graduation, they build factories and become employers of labour. Quite conversely, engineering practicals in Nigeria are largely done on the board without practical hands-on experience. The result is that Nigeria (118 t

manufacture anything after approximately six decades of independence. The country's economy remains a consumerist economy, only consuming what is imported from outside.

There is therefore, the need to steer back the direction of the African society in general and the Annang society in particular by revisiting the type of education given to our young people if the country would experience sustained progress and development.

4. Annang Indigenous Education:

The Annang indigenous education was, and still is the apprenticeship form of education. This form of education was not confined only to the Annang land, but was practiced all over Africa before the coming of the Europeans. The apprenticeship education is a form of education where the students (the apprentices) learn on the job and thereby acquire hands-on experience in the prospective profession. Uwameiye, *et. al.*, (2002:1) defined apprenticeship as "...a contractual agreement undertaken by the master-craftsman and the apprentice through which the apprentice is trained for a prescribed work process through practical experience under the supervision of the master-craftsman. It is a form of workplace learning, which enables the apprentice to have on-the-job training."

In Nigeria and all over Africa, apprenticeship has been an age-long method used in training young people in trades and crafts, agriculture, business, and catering. During the pre-colonial days, apprenticeship was the mode of training. It is a common feature of the traditional setting to see people engage in a vocation such as farming, fishing, hunting, carving, carpentry, sculpting, painting, building, decorating, smithing, catering, boat-making, mat-making, dyeing and so on. The apprenticeship system was an institution that was jealously guarded by customs, lineage and rituals. Every male born into a family was expected to learn his patrilineal craft, and it was easy to identify a young male child as a member of a lineage found to be proficient in the lineage craft (Uwameiye, *et. al.*, 2002:1).

Long before the advent of the Europeans and colonialism, the apprenticeship education has been providing training opportunities for young apprentices in Africa. In most towns and cities in Africa, mechanics' workshops, tailoring and weaving shops, etc., are very common on every street. Most adolescents who migrate from the villages to the urban areas in search for gainful employment end up signing up for apprenticeship in some of these shops for want of the white collar jobs the government promises.

When parents or the apprentice has chosen the trade in which he or she wants to professionalize in, the parents will take him or her to the shop or workshop of the master.

An agreement will be entered in specifying the fees to be paid to the master and the number of years the apprentice will undergo the training. When the conditions specified in the agreement are met, the apprentice commences his training for the agreed number of years. “The set-up for a training workshop is made up of the master (skilled), journeyman (semi-skilled), and the apprentice (unskilled)” (Uwameiye, *et. al.*, 2002:2). When the stated period for training has expired, the apprentice graduates. After graduation, the former apprentice automatically becomes a master himself or herself. Depending on the chosen trade, the graduate apprentice automatically becomes a tailor, shoe mender, seamstress, goldsmith or blacksmith, etc. He or she opens his or her shop or workshop and also takes on new apprentices.

The introduction of the 6-3-3-4 system of education in 1982, literary education was de-emphasized and the setting up of the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) in 1981 were meant to give vocational education pride of place in the schools’ curriculum. But as every government program in Nigeria, this purpose has not been followed through. The emphasis is still on a white collar orientation (as against blue collar orientation) in our educational system and paper qualification (as against hands-on experience) for job placement.

5. Conclusion

Since independence, apprenticeship education has contributed immensely to the growth of the Nigerian economy. The informal vocational training system has not only served as an indispensable complement to Western education, but also to compete with it in the provision of skilled manpower to the Nigerian economy. Most of the jobs in Nigeria are carried out by graduates of the indigenous apprenticeship scheme. The cars owned by most Nigerians are daily being repaired or serviced by roadside mechanics that have passed through the indigenous apprenticeship education. Educated Africans, including western educated engineers, patronize these graduates of the apprenticeship “schools” for the repair of their air conditioners, refrigerators, televisions, videos and other household appliances. Most of the furniture in our offices and homes are made by this same category of workers. Unfortunately, the government gives less attention to apprenticeship education.

6. Recommendation

Western education stifles the initiative of those who are not intellectually sound but may be skilful in the use of the hoe, cutlass, hammer, saw, screw driver, the smelter furnace, etc. As long as this category of people are trained and evaluated in the western st 120 education, they will continue to be passed on as dunces. But if passed through the apprenticeship education and skill acquisition training, their geniuses will appear.

Therefore, it is the recommendation of this work that those who are good in manufacturing should be trained in factories or workshops not classrooms. Engineering students should be trained with spanners and pliers, not on the white or black board.

There is need to reintroduce apprenticeship in farming, bricklaying, foundry, carpentry, etc., into the curriculum in Schools located in Annang Land. The establishment of numerous indigenous apprenticeship workshops and vocational training centers in Annang Land will provide skills to our younger generation and ultimately stem the rural-urban migration of young people looking for employment erroneously believed to be in abundance in the urban areas.

Educators in Annang land should collaborate with the Industrial Training Fund (ITF) to set up a National Apprenticeship Scheme as originally envisaged by the enabling law that established it. It should establish vocational training centers in Annang land that would provide relevant practical vocational training for both minors and employed adults.

Moreover, the original vision of the 6-3-3-4 system of education should be revisited to enable those that have no acumen for formal education to cross over to the established vocational training centers to be trained in the craft there are best fitted.

Finally, the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) should begin the proposed accreditation for roadside mechanics and so that citizens who have completed training programmes through non-formal education will be recognized and machinery should be put in motion by the government to establish, fund and equip modern workshops where these graduates of the apprenticeship education would be engaged to formally practice their trade to the benefit of Nigerians and to boost the country's GDP.

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